

Pathogenesis and virulence factors of dermatophytes - the skin eating fungi

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Dermatophytes

Arthrodermataceae (Onygenales)

- **human and animal skin pathogens**
- **characteristic lesions or onychomycosis**
- **prevalence of up to 25 % in human population**
- **easy treatment with antimycotics**
- **early identification is crucial** – *wrong medication makes infection worse*
- *growing resistance to antimycotics*
- *dissemination in severely immunocompromised patients*

Dermatophytes

Arthrodermataceae (Onygenales)

- originally saprotrophs -> decomposition of keratin in soil (skin scales, hair...)
- gradually acquired ability to **grow at body temperature and resist host immune system**
- *Trichophyton* (*Arthroderma*), *Microsporum*, *Nannizzia*, *Epidermophyton*, *Lophophyton*

- **groups according to ecology:**

 geophilic – primarily in soil, do mate sexually, opportunistic pathogens of skin

 zoophilic – pathogenic, animal-associated, broad host spectrum including human, can mate sexually

 anthropophilic – human-associated, sexual mating not observed, clonal

Dermatophytes

- well adapted to their host – able to cause asymptomatic infections
- co-evolution with mammals

„ Compared with normal hairs, such features match the so-called ‘block hairs’ and ‘i-hairs’ that represent a pathological condition associated with a fungal infection (dermatophytosis) widely spread in extant mammals“

Questions:

How do dermatophytes evade or even locally suppress the host immune system?

General virulence factors

Keratin degradation:

keratin: hydrophobic, high content of cysteine -> disulphidic bridges
-> difficult decomposition

- production of **secreted proteases** (*Sub 3*, *DPP IV*...)
- endoproteases** – cleave inside of the molecule
- exoproteases** – cleave ends of the molecule
- spectra of secreted proteases bound to **surrounding pH**
- **Ssu1** (*Sulfite efflux pump 1*)
- **Cdo1** (*cysteine dioxygenase 1*)

General virulence factors

- **secreted proteases:** *Sub 3, DPP IV, DPP V, Lap2, Mep4*
- **pH sensing**
- **growth at 37 °C**
- **adherence:** *hydrophobins and secreted proteases*
- **melanization:** *protection from stress and immune system*
- **LysM domain-containing proteins:** *bind molecules of chitin (released during growth)*
- **protection from immune system:** *escape from macrophages (penetration); production of immunomodulatory secondary metabolites -> **vioxanthin, neosartoricin B***

Questions:

What are the drivers behind host specificity?

Microsporium canis (not felis)

Asymptomatic

VS

Symptomatic

Trichophyton benhamiae complex as a model group

- zoophilic
- previously *Arthroderma benhamiae*

Trichophyton benhamiae complex as a model group

- highly related taxa (distinguishable by microsatellites)
- share host spectrum
- differ in phenotype

Sudden increase in the incidence of human and animal infections in Europe after 2010.

Methods

RT-qPCR, RNAseq – transcriptome analysis -> mouse skin explants

Analysis of secondary metabolites:

SPME/GC-MS, SPME/GCxGC-TOF MS

HPLC

LC-MS

Testing of bioactive potential

RT-qPCR analysis of 16 genes

Known virulence factors:

Secreted proteases (*subtilisin 3, dipeptidyl peptidase IV, dipeptidyl peptidase V, leucine aminopeptidase 2, aspartic-type endopeptidase*) → **NO DIFFERENCE**

Glyoxylate cycle (*malate synthase, isocitrate lyase*) → **NO DIFFERENCE**

Genes based on pilot RNAseq:

Secondary metabolism (*cytochrome p450 monooxygenase, catalase Eas C, conidial pigment polyketide synthase PksP/Alb1, lovB-like polyketide synthase, fasciclin domain family protein*)

Growth (*class III chitinase ChiA 2, 1,3-beta-glucanosyltransferase*)

Other (*GPI anchored CFEM family protein*)

RT-qPCR

Secondary metabolism (ARB_07534, ARB_07991)

DIFFERENCE!!!

a)

Similarity %	Gene
96.59	Fasciclin domain-containing protein
92.80	Flavin-binding protein
90.36	Flavin-dependent monooxygenase
92.32	Laccase
96.26	Methyltransferase
95.96	Non-reducing polyketide synthase
93.58	Short chain dehydrogenase/reductase
93.46	Transcription factor
97.65	Transporter

b)

Gene
Adenosine deaminase domain-containing protein
Autophagy-related protein 2
Cytochrome P450
FAD binding monooxygenase
Non-reducing polyketide synthase nscA
Polyketide synthase
Probable secreted aspartic protease
Serine-rich protein
Transcription factor domain-containing protein
Uncharacterized protein

Volatile secondary metabolites (GC-MS, GCxGC-TOF MS)

Robust dataset: 15 species, 47 isolates
Semi-natural conditions (sheep wool)

Differentiation of closely related taxa based on their VOC fingerprint

Machová L, Gaida M, Semerád J, Kolařík M, Švarcová M, Jašica A, Grasserová A, Awokunle Hollá S, Hubka V, Stefanuto PH, Cajthaml T, Focant JF, Wennrich A. 2025. First step on the way to identify dermatophytes using odour fingerprints. *Mycopathologia* 190.1:1–17.

Dermatophytes produce **terpenes** and compounds containing **sulfur** and **chlorine**

Bioactive potential of volatile metabolites

Compound N°	Fungi										Bacteria			
	Rhizopus oryzae		Mucor hiemalis		Aspergillus fumigatus		Candida albicans		Cryptococcus neoformans		Escherichia coli		Kocuria rhizophila	
	broth	agar	broth	agar	broth	agar	broth	agar	broth	agar	broth	agar	broth	agar
2	100	100	50	100	100	100	25	12.5	6.25	12.5	100	100	N. I.	N. I.
4	<1.57	3.13	6.25	3.13	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	12.50	3.13	N. I.	50	100	100
5	25	12.5	12.5	50	12.5	50	3.13	6.25	3.13	1.57	100	N. I.	N. I.	N. I.
9	50	100	12.5	25	50	12.5	100	N. I.	100	N. I.	100	100	N. I.	N. I.
10	50	100	12.5	25	50	50	100	N. I.	100	N. I.	100	100	N. I.	N. I.
16	50	12.5	25	25	100	100	6.25	3.13	3.13	3.13	100	N. I.	N. I.	100
17	6.25	12.5	3.13	6.25	6.25	6.25	3.13	3.13	3.13	3.13	12.5	25	50	N. I.
21	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	N. I.	N. I.	100	100
28	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	<1.57	N. I.	N. I.	6.25	12.5
52	N. I.	12.5	N. I.	N. I.	N. I.	N. I.	N. I.	N. I.	N. I.	N. I.	N. I.	N. I.	N. I.	N. I.
AMB	3.13	N. I.	0.63	N. I.	2.5	N. I.	1.25	N. I.	2.5	N. I.	-	-	-	-
CHL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.63	N. I.	3.13	N. I.

4 = 2-Methyl-3-(methylthio) furan; 21 = 4-Methylguaiacol; 28 = 4-Ethylguaiacol; 52 = Caryophyllene; AMB = Amphotericin B; CHL = Chloramphenicol; [$\mu\text{g/ml}$]

Caryophyllene: anti-inflammatory

HPLC

- *T. benhamiae* - very low production of secondary metabolites in liquid media
- Compounds new to science
- Compounds still waiting for structure determination (NMR)

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Hemavellone B

new compound

Bacillusamide B

new compound

ca. 1 : 1

new compound

■ Detection and quantification of known compounds [ng/g]

	Ergot alkaloids			Xanthomegnin synthesis	
	Chanoclavine	Rugulovasine A	Tryprostatin B	semi Xanthomegnin	Xanthomegnin
<i>T. benhamiae</i> var. <i>benhamiae</i>	0.075	nd	nd	0.185	129.510
	0.091	nd	nd	0.199	251.220
	0.100	nd	nd	0.118	261.990
<i>T. benhamiae</i> var. <i>luteum</i>	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
<i>T. europaeum</i>	nd	nd	nd	0.313	200.370
	nd	nd	nd	0.097	2681.700
	nd	nd	nd	0.149	4890.000
<i>T. japonicum</i>	9.597	0.269	0.638	0.087	897.600
	18.210	0.295	0.864	0.094	1029.600
	23.376	nd	1.102	0.146	2030.100

“Emodin family” metabolites

	Emodin	Fallacinol	Iso-Rhodoptilometrin	Penipurdin A
<i>T. benhamiae</i> var. <i>benhamiae</i>	1.218	0.684	1.083	44.220
	1.367	0.842	1.268	48.780
	0.964	0.698	0.875	35.160
<i>T. benhamiae</i> var. <i>luteum</i>	nd	nd	nd	nd
	nd	nd	nd	nd
	nd	nd	nd	nd
<i>T. europaeum</i>	nd	nd	nd	nd
	nd	nd	nd	nd
	nd	nd	nd	nd
<i>T. japonicum</i>	nd	nd	nd	nd
	nd	nd	nd	nd
	nd	nd	nd	nd

Ergot alkaloids: immunomodulation

Xanthomegnin: interferes with cellular respiratory processes

Emodin: antiviral, anti-inflammatory

Take-home message

- **Dermatophytes:**

- *common skin pathogens*

- *important but understudied group of fungi*

- **Secondary metabolites:**

- *possible main virulence factor*

- *modulation of host immunity and skin microbiome competition*

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